

EFFECTIVENESS OF STRUCTURED TEACHING PROGRAM ON KNOWLEDGE REGARDING CHILDHOOD OBESITY AND HEALTHY EATING AMONG MOTHERS

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ABSTRACT: Childhood obesity has been increasing over the past few decades and has become a public health concern in both developed and developing countries. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching program designed to enhance mothers' understanding of childhood obesity and healthy eating. The research design selected for the study was pre experimental one group pre test post- test design. Sample comprised of 100 primary school teachers of selected schools of Indore, (M.P.) selected using non probability purposive sampling technique. Structured Knowledge Questionnaire was used to assess the knowledge. The mean of post-test knowledge scores regarding childhood obesity and healthy eating among mothers was 19, which is significantly higher than mean of pre-test knowledge scores of 7.70. standard deviation of post-test score and pre-test score is 2.948 and 6.09 respectively. The computed paired “t” value (13.67, df=119, at the level of $p= 0.001$) is greater than table value (1.7) which represents significant gain knowledge through structured teaching program. This study result implies that structured teaching program was useful in improving the knowledge of mothers regarding childhood obesity and healthy eating.

Keywords: Childhood obesity, Parents

INTRODUCTION

Obesity is defined as a condition where excess body fat negatively effects on health. Childhood overweight and obesity are global problems; obesity in childhood appears to increase risk of subsequent morbidity. 30% of totally obesity is recorded in children out of which 50% to 80% leading to obesity in adults. Adulthood outcomes related to childhood obesity includes hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, left ventricular hypertrophy, non alcoholic steatohepatits, obstructive sleep apnea, orthopedic and psychosocial problems. Childhood obesity is a growing concern in India, particularly in low and middle-income populations, is expected to account for 11% of the global burden of child obesity by 2030.

Childhood obesity has been increasing over the past few decades and has become a public health concern in both developed and developing countries. Global estimates indicate that 43 million children were overweight and obese in the year 2010. More than one-fifth of overweight and obese children were from developing countries. Globally, the prevalence of overweight is expected to increase from 6.7% in 2010 to

more than 9% in 2020 compared to the increase from 8.5% to 12.7% in Africa within the same span of time.

The World Obesity Federation (WOF) and the World Health Organization (WHO) report that nearly 2.6 billion people globally are struggling with excessive body weight, including more than 1 billion with obesity. These organizations pay particular attention to the prevalence of the problem among the youngest part of the population—preschool children. In accordance with current statistics, approximately 39 million people included in this group suffer from obesity. According to predictions, if the situation does not improve, the number of people suffering from obesity will rise to around 1.9 billion by 2035. It is worth highlighting the fact that excessive body weight will be increasingly recognized not only among adults but also among children. As stated by some experts, around 400 million children could face this problem in the next 12 years. Moreover, the WHO warns that around 167 million people will deal with health risks as a result of being overweight or obese.

The low level of knowledge about the causes and consequences of excessive body weight leads to its misconception as a “temporary condition”. It is worth noting that even in the medical field, and more specifically in the paediatric field, obesity and overweight are not recognised as separate disease entities and therefore children burdened by them are not usually qualified for medical intervention. This view is inconsistent with the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Health Problems (ICD-11) effective from 01 January 2022. It has been adopted by the WHO and defines obesity and overweight as diseases, assigning them the designations 5B81 and 5B80.0.

World Health Organization WHO (1026) estimates, 41 million children below five years of age and more than 340 million adolescents in the age group of 5 to 19 years were having overweight or obesity.

Taking preventive measures and carrying out examinations in the indicated area is significant because it allows us to minimize the risk of later complications and thus to achieve a higher quality of life. Therefore, the aim of this study was the assessment of the relationship between parental knowledge and dietary behaviour and the prevalence of overweight and obesity in preschool children.

PROBLEM STATEMENT:-

A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding childhood obesity and healthy eating among mothers in selected community areas of Indore (M.P.).

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:-

1. To assess the pre test knowledge regarding childhood obesity and healthy eating among mothers.
2. To assess the post test knowledge regarding childhood obesity and healthy eating among mothers.
3. To assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding childhood obesity and healthy eating among mothers.
4. To find an association between pre-test knowledge with selected demographic variables.

HYPOTHESIS:-

RH₁ – There will be significant difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge score regarding regarding childhood obesity and healthy eating among mothers at the level of $p \leq 0.05$

RH₂ – There will be a significant association of pre-test knowledge score with selected socio-demographical variables at the level of $p \leq 0.05$.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH APPROACH: The approach used in the present study was quantitative approach. Quantitative approach most often uses deductive logic, in which researcher start with hypothesis and then collects data which can be used to determine whether empirical evidence to support that hypothesis exists.

RESEARCH DESIGN: The research design selected for the study was pre experimental one group pre test post- test design. It judges the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding childhood obesity and healthy eating among mothers by the difference of mother’s pre and post test knowledge score.

Diagrammatic representation of the design is given below

O₁ : Pre Test

X : Intervention

O₂ : Post Test

SAMPLE & SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: The present study the sample comprised of 120 mothers in selected community areas of Indore, M.P. Non probability convenient sampling technique was used.

CRITERIA FOR THE SELECTION OF THE SAMPLES

Inclusion Criteria

- Mothers staying in rural community areas
- Mothers of children (1-18 years).
- Mothers who can read and write.
- Mothers who are willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Mothers who are not willing to participate in the study.
- Mothers of urban community areas

DESCRIPTION OF TOOL

Section A (Demographic variable)- In the present study it includes Age, Family Income, Educational Qualification, Occupation of parents, Number of Children, Type of family, Type of Diet, Previous Knowledge.

Section B (Structured Knowledge Questionnaire)- In this study self-structured multiple choice questions was considered appropriate for assessing knowledge score. The test items were objective type consisting of multiple choice questions (MCQs) with one correct answer. Every correct answer was awarded a score of one (1) and every wrong answer was assigned a zero (0) score. The maximum total score of the knowledge questionnaire was 21.

Score was graded as follows:

SCORE	REMARK
0-7	Poor
8-14	Average
14-21	Good

VALIDATION AND RELIABILITY OF THE TOOL: The tool was submitted to 5 experts from the field of child health nursing along with the blue print criteria checklist, answer key, module to establish the content validity. The reliability was calculated using split half method. The tool was found reliable $r = 0.83$ using Karl Pearson formula. The tool found to be clear and understandable.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE: The investigator obtained written permission from the concerned authority prior to the data collection at the schools. Pre test knowledge was assessed using structured knowledge questionnaire to assess the existing knowledge of mothers on the first day. On the same day structured teaching program was done among the samples the date for the post test was priorly informed to them. Post test assessment was done using the same questionnaire among the mothers after 5 days.

RESULT AND INTERPRETATION

Table NO. 1Frequency and percentage distribution of mothers according to their demographic variable

SL.NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
1.	Age of mother		
	a) >20 year	24	20.0
	b) 21-30 year	92	76.7
	c) 31-40 year	04	3.3
	d) <41 year	00	00
2	Family Income:-		
	a) <10000Rs	108	90.0
	b) 10001-15000	12	10.0
	c) 15001-20000	00	0.0
	d) >20001	00	0.0

3	Educational Qualification:- a) Illiterate b) Primary School c) Higher Secondary School d) Graduate and Post graduate	20 44 36 20	16.7 36.7 30.0 16.7
4	Parent's occupation a) Unemployed b) Self employed c) Private jobs d) Government jobs	44 28 24 24	36.7 23.3 20.0 20.0
5	Number of Children:- a) 01 b) 02 c) 03 d) 04 or more	94 26 00 00	78.3 21.7 0.0 0.0
7	Types of family:- a) Joint b) Nuclear c) Extended	28 30 02	46.7 50.0 3.3
8	Types of Diet:- a) Vegetarian b) Non – Vegetarian c) Others	36 78 06	30.0 65.0 5.0

9	Previous Knowledge		
	a) Yes, Specify.....	26	21.7
	b) No	94	78.3

Age of the mothers in that 24(20%) of mothers were below 20 years, majority of 92(76.7%) of parents belongs to age group between 21-30 years, 04(3.3%) of parents were belongs to 31-40 years and no parents were in age group <41 year.

In regard to **family income** the majority of them were 108(90%) earning between below 10,000 followed by 12(10%) were owning 10001-15000 salary, 00(00%) earn in 15001-20000 and in above 20,001 were belonging to 0(0%).

Educational Qualification shows that majority 44(36.7%) belonged to Primary School followed by 36(30%) belonged to Higher Secondary school and 20(16.7%) were belonged to illiterate and graduate and post graduate.

In regard to **Number of children** those who were in 01 child 94(78.3%), 26(21.7%) were in 02 child and 03 or 4 or more both no sample.

In regard to **type of family** the majority of them are nuclear family 60(50%) followed by joint family 56(46.7%) and in extended family 4(3.3%)

Types of diet, shows the majority 78 (65%) from Non- Veg followed by 36(30%) from Veg , and 06(05%) from Mixed diet.

Previous Knowledge 94(78.3%) had No previous knowledge and 26(21.7%) had previous knowledge. 26 who have previous knowledge got it from health care members and family.

COMPARISON OF PRE TEST AND POST TEST LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE OF MOTHERS

Table No. 2 Comparison of Pre-Test and Post-Test Knowledge Score

	Pre test	Post test

Level of knowledge	Frequency	Percentage %	Frequency	Percentage %
Poor (01-07)	78	65	-	-
Average (08-14)	36	30	12	10
Good (15-21)	06	05	108	90
Total	120	100	120	100

The pre test knowledge score toddler diet was poor 78(65%), Average 36(30%) and Good 6(5%).whereas post-test knowledge score was Average in 12(10%), good in 108(90%) parents and none of them had poor knowledge after the structured teaching program.

Fig 1 : Bar diagram represents percentage distribution of pre-test and post test level of knowledge regarding structured teaching program Among mothers

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE STRUCTURED TEACHING PROGRAM ON KNOWLEDGE REGARDING CHILDHOOD OBESITY AND HEALTHY EATING

Table No.3 Effectiveness of the structured teaching program on knowledge regarding childhood obesity and healthy eating

Test	Mean	Standard deviation	“t” value
Pre test	7.70	6.09	“t” _{cal} =13.67 df=119 “t” _{tab} =1.7 p=0.001 HS
Post test	19.00	2.948	

HS* highly significant, df –degree of freedom

The mean of post-test knowledge scores regarding structured teaching program among mothers was 19, which is significantly higher than mean of pre-test knowledge scores of 7.70. standard deviation of post-test score and pre-test score is 2.948 and 6.09 respectively. The computed paired “t” value (13.67, df=119, at the level of p= 0.001) is greater than table value (1.7) which represents significant gain knowledge through structured teaching program. Hence the hypothesis (H₁) is accepted.

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN PRE TEST KNOWLEDGE SCORES WITH THEIR SELECTED DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES.

Table No. 4 Association between demographic variables and pre test level of knowledge

Particular	Pre-Test Score			df	χ^2 value
	Poor	Average	Good		
Age					
>20 year	50	40	02	04	0.878 Insignificant (p=0.05)
21-30years	20	04	00		
31-40years	04	00	00		
<41 year	00	00	00		
Family Income					
>10000	50	56	02	06	1.629 Insignificant (p=0.05)
10001-15000	06	06	00		
150001-20000	00	00	00		
<20001	00	00	00		
Mothers Occupation					
Unemployed	42	02	00	06	17.5 Significant (p=0.05*)
Self employed	14	20	02		
Private job	12	10	02		
Government Job	10	12	02		
Educational Qualification					

Illiterate	18	02	00	06	3.562 Insignificant (p=0.05)
Primary School	34	08	02		
Higher Secondary School	28	06	02		
Graduate & Post graduate	18	02	00		
Number Of children					
01	50	40	04	04	2.125 Insignificant (p=0.05)
02	24	02	00		
03	00	00	00		
04 or More	00	00	00		
Type of family					
Joint	26	20	10	02	9.378 Significant (p=0.009*)
Nuclear	30	26	04		
Extended	02	02	00		
Type of Diet					
Veg	20	14	02	01	3.485 Insignificant (P=0.004*)
Non-Veg	30	38	10		
Mixed	02	04	00		

Previous Knowledge					
Yes	16	08	02	02	4.085
No	50	40	04		Significant (p=0.05*)

X^2 =chi-square *= Significant

The association of pre-test knowledge score with their selected demographic variables by using chi-square(x^2), it was evident that there was significant association between pre-test knowledge score with selected demographic variable.

CONCLUSION

The mean of post-test knowledge scores regarding dietary guidelines of toddler among parents was 19, which is significantly higher than mean of pre-test knowledge scores of 7.70. standard deviation of post-test score and pre-test score is 2.948 and 6.09 respectively. The computed paired “t” value (13.67, df=119, at the level of $p= 0.001$) is greater than table value(1.7) which represents significant gain knowledge through nutritional educational package. Thus the “RH₁: There will be significant difference between pre test knowledge and post test knowledge score regarding childhood obesity and healthy eating among parents at the level of $p\leq 0.05$. is accepted.

it is evident from the results that RH₂: There will be significant association between the pre test knowledge score and selected demographic variables at the level of $p\leq 0.05$. is accepted as there is significant association between pretest knowledge score and selected demographic variables like Mothers occupation, previous knowledge and type of family.

From the above results, we can conclude that there was a statistically significant in gaining knowledge regarding child obesity and healthy eating among mothers. Thus, the intervention “structured teaching program ” was effective.

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